

Supplementary material for the article published in *Clinical & Experimental Allergy*:

Lymphopenia in chronic spontaneous urticaria is linked to basopenia and eosinopenia

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METHODS

Laboratory parameters and the autologous serum skin test

Results of the following laboratory tests performed at Clinic Golnik laboratory were collected: automated complete blood count (**CBC**) with differential ($n=300$; Sysmex XN 3100, Sysmex), C-reactive protein (**CRP**; $n=292$; Cobas 6000, Roche Diagnostics), total serum immunoglobulin E (**total IgE**; $n=149$; Immulite 2000Xpi, Siemens Healthcare Diagnostics), immunoglobulin G against thyroid peroxidase (**anti-TPO**; $n=184$; Cobas 6000, Roche Diagnostics), antinuclear antibody test (**ANA**; $n=86$; Fluorescent ANA test system, Immuno Concepts) and immunoglobulin G against complement component C1q (**anti-C1q**; $n=81$; ELISA, Bühlmann Laboratories AG). The cut-off values were $<1.5 \times 10^9/L$ for lymphopenia,¹ $<0.01 \times 10^9/L$ for basopenia,² $<0.05 \times 10^9/L$ for eosinopenia,^{2,3} ≥ 5.0 mg/L for high CRP,⁴ <40 IU/mL for low total IgE,⁵ ≥ 34 kU/L for high anti-TPO⁵ and ≥ 15 U/mL for high anti-C1q. The autologous serum skin test (**ASST**, $n=110$) was performed according to the EAACI/GA²LEN task force consensus report.⁶

Statistical analysis

Data from electronic medical records and patient charts were collected and analysed using IBM Statistical Package for the Social Sciences software (SPSS) version 25. Categorical variables were presented with frequencies and percentages and were analysed using Fisher's exact test. The Kolmogorov-Smirnov test was used to assess data normality. Numerical variables were expressed as either means with SD or medians with interquartile ranges (IQR). The Student's t-test and the Mann-Whitney test were used for variables that were normally and not normally distributed, respectively. The rank correlation coefficient (Spearman's *rho* [r]) was interpreted as follows:

weak ($r = 0.10-0.29$), moderate ($r = 0.30-0.50$), and strong ($r > 0.50$).⁷ A p -value of less than 0.05 was considered statistically significant.

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